

EXPERIENCES OF IMMIGRANTS IN LATVIA: CHALLENGES AND WAY FORWARD

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***Abstract.** The concept of migration is as old as humanity. It involves the movement of people from one place to another in search of safety, health, and a better life. Although migration comes with many challenges, it is reported that the number of people leaving their country of birth for another country is increasingly consistent. While there are several literatures on immigrants across Europe, not much have been researched about immigrants in Latvia especially from the African and Asian descent. Importantly, most recommendations or course for action for the immigrant's population have always come from the coffers of authority, agencies, and other organizations. Due to this occurrence, this study obtained recommendations from the perspectives of immigrants on how they can be better positioned and helped to successfully integrate into the culture and lifestyle of their host country. This study also explored the experiences of immigrants, highlighting the challenges they encounter which has inhibited their smooth integration as immigrants in Latvia. This is a qualitative research design with semi-structured interview which utilized a purposive sampling technique. The study participants were Nine (9) immigrants residing in Latvia for at least 2 years and above. The data for this study was analyzed manually. The research took the nature of thematic analysis. The data were analyzed into broad themes and sub-themes. The study found that immigrants in Latvia face series of difficulties including low pay, discrimination, and poor housing, among others. Learning the host country's language and establishment*

of locals-immigrants' social activities were recommended as a strategy which with potential to foster social cohesion among citizens and immigrants in Latvia. In conclusion, governmental support and immigrant's effort are a good recipe for the successful integration of immigrants in Latvia.

Keywords: *Immigrant, Challenges, Migration, Latvia, Experience*

Background

Migration is not a recent phenomenon (European Investment Bank, 2016); it has been explored from different perspectives and has several ramifications for life. In the context of Latvia, for a long time, especially during the soviet and little after the soviet period, emigration was the order of the day for the citizen of Latvia (Kaša & Mieriņa, 2019). However, during the past few years, shortly after Latvia joined the European Union (European Union, 2014), there has been a mass exodus from Asia, the Middle East and Africa descents largely due to economic and educational purposes. Latvia and other European countries have become more popular destinations for large migration movements. Nationals of other EU nations and citizens of non-EU nations are choosing to visit or settle in Latvia on a temporary or permanent basis due to the country's growing allure. In 2013, nearly three times as many persons—representing nearly all immigrant groups—as there were ten years ago when only about 2,000 people applied for a residence visa valid for up to five years. There are three times as many persons choosing to study in Latvia today as there were ten years ago, as well as those looking to apply for asylum (European Union, 2014). The quality of life for Latvians since joining the EU has increased phenomenally, and that has attracted large-scale of migrants (European Union, 2014).

According to European Investment Bank (2016), In 2014, about 12.2% of the population in Latvia was non-EU born. This represents immigrants from different parts of the world, especially Asians and Africans. Three factors, such as fertility, mortality, and migration, affect the population of any nation. Migration can be fluid, continuous, non-discrete, and poorly defined, it is the most challenging to quantify.

Migration is, broadly speaking, the act of moving from one location to another. To migrate is to relocate, whether it is from a countryside to an urban setting, from one region or region to another within the same nation, or from one nation to another (McAuliffe & Triandafyllidou, 2022). It simply entails movement. Sometimes these movements are carefully planned; other times, they are forced. The International Organization for Migration (IOM) 2015 defines Migration as “the movement of a person or a group of people, either inside a country or over an international border”. Any migration of people, regardless of number, composition, or motivation, is considered a population movement. This includes the emigration of refugees, internally displaced people, economic migrants, and those travelling for other motivations, such as family reunions. Although the definition of Migrant seems unclear across many literatures, The UN defines a migrant as "someone who changes his or her country of regular residence, regardless of the reason for migration or legal status" in this context.

Across several pieces of literature, the challenges of immigrants have been captured across populated cities in major European countries like Germany, France, Italy and Sweden. However, due to the dearth of literature about studies of immigrants in Latvia, not much information has been disclosed about the situation of Immigrants of African and Asian descent in Latvia, especially as there are more immigrants from this region. Hence the need for this study to deeply investigate the experience of immigrants who has been residing in Latvia for three years or more. The significance of this study is to first contribute to data on immigrant’s experience from Latvia and suggest possible ways to solve the increasing and emerging problems of immigrants in Latvia. With this study, social workers, policymakers, volunteers, youth workers, and all professionals working with immigrants in Latvia will be aware of the experience of immigrants and develop an effective protocol for working with immigrants to provide an enriching experience for immigrants in Latvia.

The overall aim of this study was to explore the challenges of migration from the experience of immigrants in Latvia and obtaining way forward. The objectives of the study were premised on three broad areas such as 1) To investigate the lived experience of immigrants in Latvia, 2) To identify the key challenges of immigrants in Latvia, 3) To extract solutions to the identified challenges from the lens of immigrants in Latvia. Furthermore, three overarching questions were asked in this study; 1) What are the experiences of immigrants in Latvia? What are the key challenges faced by immigrants in Latvia? and, 3) From the perspectives of immigrants in Latvia, what are the panaceas to the challenges they encounter?

Theoretical Perspectives of Migration

The Neoclassical Theory of Migration

It is important to acknowledge that a significant body of literature has explored migrations from several theoretical perspectives with a similar goal of finding a base for arguments. Robert Solow and Trevor Swan in 1956 founded this theory. With its core assumption that migration is largely caused by economic assessments of relative advantages and costs, including financial and psychological costs, the Neoclassical theory was one of the earliest theories that had a considerable effect on migration (De Haas, 2010). The basic template of neoclassical theory emphasizes that migration is determined by factors such as interregional wage disparities, the distance between origin and destination, and labour market conditions such as the unemployment rate from the region where the immigrants come from. According to the Neoclassical theory, an individual's decision to migrate or become an immigrant in another country is first and foremost because of income maximization and employment (Xiana & Prieto-rosas, 2019). Although, this theory continues to receive backlash and several criticisms because it only considers the financial part of migration, thereby ignoring other aspects of migration, such as legal, cultural, and family issues. Regardless of the criticism, it best fits this study because it explains why the participant in this study migrated from his country because he wanted a job with higher pay than where he came from. The overall emphasis of this theory is that people migrate because they

want economic growth, and this economic growth may be difficult in their country of origin due to several factors, especially those coming from low-and-middle-income countries; therefore, they seek countries with better economic opportunities (Massey et al., 2011).

The Push and Pull Theory or Lee's Theory

Spurgeon, Everett Lee, Professor of Sociology at the University of Georgia, is well-known for developing the Push and Pull theory, often known as Lee's Theory. Lee originally introduced his idea at the Mississippi Valley Historical Association's Annual Meeting in Kansas City in 1965 (Lee, E. 1966). Conditions that might cause individuals to leave their homes and are connected to the nation from which a person migrates are referred to as push factors (Nicholas et al., 2017). Push factors include a lack of sufficient livelihood possibilities, poverty, natural disasters, fast population expansion that exceeds available resources, primeval or poor living conditions, desertification, famines/droughts, fear of political persecution, insufficient social support, inadequate healthcare, financial loss, and natural catastrophes (Parkins, N. C. 2010, Nicholas et al., 2017). Meanwhile, Pull factors are exactly the opposite of push factors—they attract people to a certain location (Nicholas et al., 2017). Typical examples of pull factors of a place are more job opportunities and better living conditions; easy availability of land for settling and agriculture; political and/or religious freedom; superior education and welfare systems, better transportation and communication facilities, better healthcare system and stress-free environment attractive, and security (Parkins, N. C. 2010, Nicholas et al., 2017). According to Everett Lee (Lee, E. 1966)., the variables connected with the choice to migrate, and the process of migration are classified into four separate components: (1) Variables connected to the immigrant original place; (2) Variables relating to the target country; (3) Mediating impediments; and (4) Personal factors.

Materials/Methods

Research Design

This study adopted a cross-sectional qualitative approach to help understand every aspect of the participant's experience as immigrants in Latvia. Semi-structured interviews were used to ask relevant questions to the participants in order to stay on course with the information related to the aim of the study and to give participants the chance to give more information and not be rigid in their responses.

Study Area

This study was conducted in Riga, Latvia. Riga is the capital city of Latvia with about 605,802 people, or one-third of Latvia's population, living in the area, the country's capital and largest city (Investment and Tourism agency of Riga, 2020). At the point where the Daugava River empties into the Baltic Sea, the city is located on the Gulf of Riga. The area of Riga is 307.17 km² (118.60 sq mi) in size, and it is situated on a sandy plain 1–10 m (3.3–32.8 ft) above sea level. Riga was a previous member of the Hanseatic League and was established in 1201. The historical district of Riga is a UNESCO World Heritage Site and is known for its timber construction from the 19th century and Art Nouveau/Jugendstil architecture (Anteniške, 2006). In 2014, Riga served as the European Cultural Capital. With more and more new visitors arriving daily, Riga is rising in popularity among European and international tourism destinations (Investment and Tourism agency of Riga, 2020). The language of communication is primarily Latvian or Russian.

Selection of Participants – Inclusion Criteria/Exclusion Criteria

The participants in this study were either gainfully employed or owned a business venture and has been residing in Latvia for at least two years. They also must also have a resident permit (temporal or permanent). Students or anyone residing in Latvia for less than two years were excluded from the study.

Sample Size

There were 9 participants in total used in this study. The participants were from India, Bangladesh, Ivory Coast, and Ghana.

Sample Techniques

Purposive sampling was used in selecting the participants based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Purposive sampling is a type of non-probability sampling method which explains that participants in a study are selected based on the researcher's judgement and according to the specific goal of the study.

Data Collection Method

Data for this study were collected via zoom and WhatsApp online platforms. WhatsApp voice call was also used. These choices of data collection methods were chosen as they were the most preferred choice of the participants due to work schedules. The interview sessions were recorded and transcribed afterwards. Averagely, the interview lasted for 50 minutes, and 06 seconds.

Informed Consent

Permission was obtained to record prior to the interview and a verbal informed consent was also obtained from the participants. The participants were sent a letter via email and social media handles stating the purpose of the study and voluntary participation before they participated in the study.

Confidentiality of Data

The data collected from the participants were coded using pseudonyms rather than using the participant's original name to ensure privacy is maintained. The researcher did not use the actual name or any form of identification of the participants during the analysis and publication of this study.

Autonomy

The Participants in this study had the liberty to decide whether to participate in the study or not. They were notified of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any point in time without threat or consequences.

Data Analysis

The process of organizing, analyzing, and giving meaning to the vast amount of acquired data is known as data analysis. Data analysis in the context of research

refers to a strategy or method for decomposing the gathered data. The interview was recorded with the participants' consent and later transcribed manually for data analysis. Data was analyzed manually. The analysis was done according to the aim and objectives of the study and to answer the research questions.

Findings

Demographics of the participant in this study

There were nine (9) participants which includes 5 males and 4 females. The study participants average age ranges between 27-40 years. The highest qualification attained by the participants is a master's degree.

Qualitative findings

The results of the qualitative methods, including In-depth Interviews, are presented in this section. Findings are presented based on the research objectives and summarized into both main themes and sub-themes alongside quotes that reflect each of these themes.

Research Objective one: To investigate the lived experience of an immigrant in Latvia.

The Participants' lived experience from the period of arrival in Latvia till the time of the interview was explored by an in-depth interview. Sub-themes are summarized under four broad themes, which include: (1) differences in culture (2) environmental disparities (3) experience with different forms of prejudice and 4) Foreseeable future in the host country.

Main Theme 1: The differences in culture

From the transcribed interview, the Participants in this study described the differences in culture under one sub-theme, which is Individualistic and collectivistic societies.

Sub-theme: Individualistic and collectivistic societies

From the lived experience of the research participants, the participants highlighted some differences between their home country and the host country (Latvia).

One of the participants said;

“...uhmm, I come from a culture which is welcoming and basically guests are treated like a god... i am from a very friendly culture and open... In the initial days, it was very lonely here... “people are not very interactive, so it’s all silent...”

Another one mentioned:

“In my country, people are warm and friendly, but since I came here I see how people are cold, reserve and not talking and this have greatly affected my social life”

Main theme 2: Environmental Disparities

From the analysis of the interview with the immigrants in Latvia, environmental disparities were extrapolated as a main theme. Weather conditions and population changes were extracted as a sub-theme.

Sub-theme: Weather conditions, atmosphere, and population changes

When asked about the experience so far living in Latvia, the participants recounted that part of their experiences was a huge difference between the environment and population of their country and that of the host country.

One participant highlighted that: *“...everywhere there was only building and empty streets and its so peaceful that you could hear the leaves falling... I can say the country is so peaceful and silent... rarely you see people on the streets like my country.. Latvia is a very beautiful, peaceful place to live in...You have all the lake and sea views... You have parks in the city and everywhere has a walkable distance. Very artistic designs and buildings...”*

Another participant said: *I just chose Latvia and expects that i will face some cold (winter) periods...”*

One of the participants also highlighted the following: *“when I came down from the airport, I wanted go back In the plane and go back to my country...hmmm! Tis very very cold”. Also, I was shocked that the infrastructure especially the building doesn’t look much like other European countries especially when you leave the city center.*

Main theme 3: Experience with different forms of prejudice

From the analysis of the interview with the immigrants in Latvia, discrimination and seclusion in public social places was set as a sub-theme for the different forms of prejudice.

Sub-theme: Forms of discrimination and seclusion in public social places.

Recounting their experience as immigrants in Latvia, the participants reported different forms of prejudice since moving to living in Latvia. When asked if there were any forms of discrimination, the participants had this to say.

“... Hmmm, it was more prominent in the first few years when i came here in the college, we had some greek students who came for Erasmus to my University in Riga, it was kind of a 5 day program, organized by the university, at the end of the program, we went to the Riga old town, and then we went to the club. In the club, the security guards refused to allow me to go inside the club. The other Latvians and Europeans were allowed to go in, i asked them why, they said no INDIANS” I have some of my immigrant friends and colleagues who have had similar incidents, like they told me that, they have had some kind of attacks from some Latvian people in some remote areas in Latvia, just because they speak English and not Latvian...”.

“... the good apartments are occupied by the citizens. Most people from third world country like me from India are living in a ++ bit uhmm! unhealthy apartments...”

“when I go out with my ex-girlfriend who is a Latvian, I get very scary stare from people, sometimes, they verbally harass her and tell her that what is doing with this “thing”... Are Latvia men finished in the country? It was a terrible experience and that made her quit the relationship because it was too much for her”

Main theme 4: Unforeseeable future in the host country

During the interview, due to the experience of the participants in this study, the researcher derived the theme “foreseeable future in host country” with a sub-theme “Lack of prospects”.

Sub-theme: Lack of Prospect

During the course of the interview with the participants in this study, it was discovered that the participant reported lack of interest in staying in the country for futuristic purposes due to some personal factors. This is premised on the following quotes.

“... And uhmm, as per living here for the future, i am not very happy personally with my career growth, or financial growth or even social and cultural growth. In any case i dont see growth here, it might be a different experience for different people. The only thing it is peaceful but not good for growth...”

“I don’t have the job of my dreams here, I am not sure I want to stay here for a long time, I will leave at some point when I get a better opportunity elsewhere”

Research Objective two: To identify the key challenges of immigrants in Latvia.

A variety of identified significant challenges faced by the immigrants in Latvia was observed during the interview, and this was geared to meet the research objectives of the study. There are three broad themes and sub-themes that attend to the research objectives. The broad themes are 1) cultural and communication difficulties 2) Economic Unsettlement, and 3) Housing. The findings of this objective are shown in the following sub-themes with their quotations.

Main theme 1: Cultural and communication difficulties

Finding the interview with the participants of the study, they revealed some cultural and communication challenges. There are two sub-themes under this main theme.

Sub-theme 1: Language barrier in communication

In order for effective communication to take place between two or more people, there must be an understanding. The understanding of what is said and how what is said is understood passes through a medium known as language. The immigrants shared some insights into some of the language issues they have

experienced since moving to Latvia. The following quotes reveal some of these language blockades.

“...It was also difficult for me to get information because, so many people do not even reply to you when you speak with them, even if some of them hear English, they will not respond to you..._Even in hospitals, post office, and in many other places they only speak their language, and it is difficult to find help...”

“I have been here for more than three years, and I still struggle to communicate because of the language. Most of the Latvian citizens do not understand English. You can only be their person when you speak Latvian or Russian because this is their main languages here”.

Sub-theme 2 – Intolerant citizens due to cultural disparities

Intolerance due to the obvious difference in culture was mentioned as an experience the immigrants have since arriving in Latvia.

One participant said: *“...also try to find help for yourself because you will not be able to find a friend in need from the locals when you need one... but initially it was very tough, they don’t engage with me... For me it was very challenging to get with them in the beginning...”*

“They won’t come near you to make friends with you, I think only few don’t mind coming to you. Some of the locals prefer to keep silent when they see you danger”

Main theme two – Economic unsettlement

From the analysis of the interview with the immigrant in Latvia, economic unsettlement was derived as a main theme with difficulty securing employment, protracted time to settle down due to lack of funds and low pay as the sub-themes.

Sub-theme 1: Difficulty in securing gainful employment.

Every human desire to have a good life. In order to do this successfully, gainful employment is necessary. This is not the situation of most of the immigrants in the study, as they reported difficulty in getting employed, as seen in their quotes below.

“...most of the companies in Latvia prefers to hire local people or you should have the mastery Latvian and or Russian Language which was strange to me...”

“...it is very tough for immigrants especially Indians to get Jobs here and be stable financially...”

Sub-theme 2: Protracted time to settle down.

Settling down in a new country and starting afresh requires some form of financial stability, among other factors. The participants in this study reportedly mentioned that settling down in Latvia seem like a huge challenge. This is premised on the following quotes below:

“... It takes a lot of time for you to settle here because in terms of income, it is mostly very low for foreigner...”

“It is very hard to settle early here.. Many factors are just against us immigrants. Jobs don't come in handy and as immigrants we need money to speed our settlement”

Sub-theme 3: Low pay as an immigrant/foreigner in Latvia

One of the challenges confronting immigrants in Latvia, as revealed during the interview with participants in this study, is the low wage being paid to immigrants in Latvia as compared to the wage paid to host employees. One quote reads;

“...When i say about the economic aspect first of all, Latvia has very low pay for us as immigrant especially when i came, it was very difficult for majority of the immigrants to work and make money. The earning is just for survival, for me it's like “you just keep surviving year after year...”

Main theme three – Housing issues

The study participants highlighted one of the significant setbacks in fully integrating into Latvia society is housing challenges which is exacerbated by the attitudes of some Latvian Landlords. This broad theme is characterized in three sub-themes names 1) unfair treatment by landlords, 2) Poor housing allocation, and 3) housing discrimination.

Sub-theme 1: Unfair treatment by Landlords

The participants reported unfair treatment of some landlords towards immigrants. The reason for this treatment meted specifically is not appreciated by the participants.

“...then if you want to rent an apartment in some places, most of the house owners will not give you apartment”

“just because, you are from Africa, they will not accept you. it is very hard to find apartment especially if you are from Ivory Coast...”

Sub-theme 2: Poor housing allocation

Another important drawback is poor housing. Even in cases where houses are given out, it is not best of houses are reported by one of the participants in this study during the interview.

“...Most people from third world country like me from India are living in a bit uhmm unhealthy apartments... You live in a European country here, but inside the houses are filthy...”. I have also heard similar stories from my other immigrants friends”

Sub-theme 3: Housing discrimination

There are various kinds of discrimination, and this was shown in the answer of the study participants when asked about the various kinds of discrimination experienced in Latvia. The participant has this to say.

“...The landlords raise the tenants fee very high if you're an immigrant so that you cannot afford to pay especially if you are from a third world country... they make the fee high to the point that it covers almost 40% of your income...”

Research Objectives 3: To extract a solution to the identified challenges from the lens of an immigrant in Latvia.

It is not enough to identify challenges and setbacks confronting immigrants in Latvia; it is imperative to understand how these challenges can be solved from the perspective of those experiencing these sorts of challenges. It is said that he who wears the shoes knows what part is painful. With regard to this, questions were asked

to know how the identified challenges can be resolved from the viewpoint of the study participant. This objective has three main themes and their sub-themes.

Main theme 1: Host country's commitment to foreigners.

From the perspectives of the study participants, there are some responsibilities the government and people from the host countries can shoulder in order to mitigate the challenges identified in this study. The main theme of this finding has four sub-theme that reveals how the host community can improve the situation for the immigrant.

Sub-theme 1: Job opportunity and equal pay between locals and foreigners

Making jobs easier and accessible to get for immigrants together with equal pay as the locals is what the study participant is recommending with the following quote.

“...Job opportunity for students is one recommendation...”

“...then, the income for immigrants should be increased because the locals are paid more than immigrants even when they do the same job, let say local gets 7euros per hour, immigrants get something less than 5 euros. I remember 5 years back, I worked for less than 2 euros per...” hour...”

Sub-theme 2: Easy accessibility to good housing

As with job opportunities and equal pay, the participants in this study have also mentioned that the government of Latvia can make the life of immigrants better be ensuring ease of access to quality housing. His quote reads:

“...some organizations to facilitate the accommodations issues for immigrants, the communication issues to help relationships between local and immigrants...”

Sub-theme 3: Provision of intercultural programs and activities

Intercultural activities between immigrants and the host country are a recommendation made by the study participants if immigrants must be fully integrated.

“...also, like programs or events to improve the co-cultural, interrelations of the citizens and immigrants, even some organizations who could create some activities for the mental wellbeing of those migrants who are coming in order to help them to adapt to these challenging situations...”

Main theme 2: Social support as a coping mechanism

In the face of overwhelming challenges, social support is a strong buffer to help immigrants through the process of integration or assimilation. The study participants reeled out some elements of the social support used as an immigrant in Latvia. There is only one sub-theme in this category.

Sub-theme 1: Colleagues at work, church, and friendships

Having people to care for and tend to your needs regardless of your location is a recipe for inner strength and resilience. One of the participants quoted colleagues at work, church, and having few friends in his circle as being helpful as an immigrant.

“...firstly, I was fortunate to have good connection from my company and also from my church, thirdly from some of the good friends I met from the church... Also, there were some networking, socialization events conducted by some groups I have made some friends from them...”

Main theme 3: Immigrants’ contribution to foster integration.

Integration is a concept which requires efforts from both government and citizens of host countries. The participants in this study suggested how immigrants can foster integration and better their lives. This is captured in the sub-theme.

Sub-theme 1: Learning the host country’s language.

From the interview with the study participant, it is imperative to make attempt to learn the language of the host country as seen in the quote of the participant.

“...I am an immigrant, but I tried to learn the Latvian language, in order to relate with them more, - so uhhh, ermm, now it is somehow better...”

Discussion

The section of the study describes the results of the study in relation to the research questions. The research questions are linked directly to the research aim and

research objectives, hence this part of the study focuses on discussion about research questions while connecting positively (agreeing) or negatively (disagreeing) with existing findings from other studies.

What are the experiences of immigrants in Latvia?

In this study, participants described their various experiences in Latvia since moving there as immigrants. Some of the experiences include the differences in culture which they described as being very individualistic compared to their country of origin which is largely perceived to be collectivistic. There also a vast parallel difference in weather conditions and what is obtainable in immigrants' environment and that of host country. Latvia is described where its people are cold and not so open largely because of the historical experience being under the USSR (Golubeva, 2012). The participant also described experience with different forms of discrimination in public social places. This finding corroborate with a research by (The UN Refugee Agency, 2021), where they found that Syrian refugees and immigrants experience negative attitudes from the Latvian locals. In addition, the participants in this study have experience with environmental changes in Latvia which is way different from home environment. Some of the experience with the environment include seeing the excellent architectural designs and the proximity of lakes, rivers, and parks within the city. This finding is in tandem with the findings of (Anteniške, 2006; Investment and Tourism agency of Riga, 2020) where they mentioned that Latvia especially the city of Riga is built to attract tourists from the different continents. Due to some of the negative experiences of the participants in this study, it seems as though majority of the participants do not see future in residing in Latvia for the longest possible time, therefore the participant perceives an unforeseeable future and this is also in accordance with a study conducted by Thapan & Deka, (2011) where they found that Indian immigrants in developed country such as Latvia, France and other European countries usually do not stay back in a host country if their financial, social, educational career or professional growth is stunted.

What are the key challenges faced by immigrants in Latvia?

In this research, the participants specifically referred to vital challenges faced as immigrants in Latvia. These challenges include language and communication barriers, intolerant and negative attitudes from the Latvian citizens, housing challenges such as negative treatment from landlords, inconsiderate and unnecessary increase of rent bills and poor allocation of rooms. These findings about the vital challenges reported by the participants in this study is also found in several research conducted in some European countries where the researchers also found commonalities in the challenge's immigrants faced in those countries. For example, studies by Sami (2000), Thapan & Deka (2011) Zepa (2001) Zepa et al., (2009) show that immigrants in Latvia are exposed and extensively susceptible to being victimized when looking for accommodation, attacked verbally, cheated, overused at the workplace, and discriminated upon. The participants in this study also mentioned other challenges, which includes the overly extended time it takes to settle down in the host country, the lack of jobs for immigrants and even in the case where there are jobs, the immigrants are paid lower than the citizens which seem unjust and further strengthen the concept of social dumping in Latvia. Social dumping is described as the practice of providing workers (especially migrants workers) with inferior or poorer wages and/or working and housing situations compared to those established by law or collective agreements in the relevant labour market (Bernaciak, 2015).

From the perspective of immigrants in Latvia, what are the panaceas to the challenges immigrants encounter?

The participants in this research beckoned on the government of Latvia and international organizations resident in Latvia to make jobs easier and accessible to immigrants with the same pay as the locals. The recommendation is corroborated by several studies done by (Aļeksējeva & Auškāps, 2019; Ekmanis, 2017; Ilona et al., 2009; Tabuns et al., 2011; University of Latvia Press, 2010) where the researchers found that government change in the integration labour policy would make it easier, and quicker for immigrants to get Jobs, settle fast and integrate successfully in their

host countries. Additionally, the participants in this study suggested that accessibility to good housing, immigrants' effort in learning the local language, orientations for Latvian citizens and development of intercultural activities between immigrants and locals is essential in mitigating or solving the identified challenges for immigrants in Latvia. All these recommendations are recipes for smooth integration. In the same vein (Anastasopoulou & Iliadis, 2015; Economic and Social Council, 2018; FFH, 2018; Kährik et al., 2019; Poon & Garratt, 2012) suggested that in order for immigrants to overcome challenges of migration and completely integrate into the host community, certain parameters must be in place. Parameters such as good housing scheme, free language literacy classes, social and intercultural activities as well as education for citizens beginning from young age about migration, tolerance, and co-existence of other nationalities. Furthermore, the participants in this study asserted that having emotional, instrumental and all dimensions of social support is a good way to overcome some of these challenges. Kort-Butler, (2017) highlighted that social support is a fundamental tool that can be used to overcome any difficulty.

Recommendation and Future Work

In order to improve the lived experiences of immigrants, intercultural activities geared towards uniting immigrants and members of the host countries should be established, implemented and sustained.

Integration is two broad traffic, as such, the immigrants have a responsibility to ensure that they respect all the rules and regulation of the host countries and participates actively in intercultural activities. Immigrants are also encouraged to establish communities of their own within the host countries for social support.

Further research can investigate interviewing citizens of the host countries to also obtain their perception and experience with immigrants. By doing this, there will be an avenue for a balanced story between immigrants in Latvia and members of the host country.

Conclusion

It is interesting to dig deep into the experience's immigrants in Latvia. This study shows the overall experiences of immigrants, including the challenges and solutions from the perspective of the immigrants. It is not new that immigrants are faced with setbacks, especially in the process of integration; however, these setbacks in integration for the immigrants can be turned into steppingstone for successful integration if there is an equal or at least an effort from both the immigrants in Latvia and the government or people from the host country (Latvia). It is imperative to note that policy review and reformation could be helpful in improving this situation.

References:

1. Aļeksējeva, M., & Auškāps, T. (2019). *Low-Skilled Immigrant Employment In Latvia . Employer Perspective* (Vol. 12, Issue November).
2. Anastasopoulou, G., & Iliadis, C. (2015). Migrants and their Descendants: Social Inclusion and Participation in Society - Greece. In *FRANET Report*. <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/?action=media.download&uuid=9CA6B9D6-A401-C065-24156857731A3B12%0Apapers3://publication/uuid/90AAAD1D-94B5-4615-A7BF-E768FAC6339E>
3. Antenišķe, A. (2006). National Romanticism Apartment Buildings of Riga. In *Reseau Art Nouveau Network*.
4. Bernaciak, M. (2015). Introduction: Social dumping and the EU integration process. *Market Expansion and Social Dumping in Europe*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315766607>
5. Economic and Social Council. (2018). *Housing for Migrants : Challenges and Practices in the ECE Region* (Issue October 2017).
6. Ekmanis, I. D. (2017). Host Land or Homeland?: Civic-Cultural Identity and Banal Integration in Latvia. *ProQuest Dissertations and Theses*, 245. <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1944516168?accountid=9645>

7. European Investment Bank. (2016). *Migration and the EU - challenges opportunities, the role of EIB*.

8. EUKN. 2016. Working Conference on Reception and Housing of Migrants and Refugees, 10–11 November, Amsterdam.

9. EWSI. 2016. EWSI Analysis: Immigrant Housing in Europe, European Commission [Online]. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/intdossier/ewsi-analysis-immigrant-housing-in-europe>

10. Eurostat. Migration and migrant population statistics - Statistics Explained. 2015. Available from: http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Migration_and_migrant_population_statistics Cited 2018 Dec 4.

11. The conclusions from this meeting can be found at http://www.europarl.europa.eu/summits/tam_en.htm. 86

12. For the EC's communication on this matter, see <http://eurlex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2000:0757:FIN:EN:PDF>

13. 87 Find the Lisbon Strategy at http://europa.eu/scadplus/glossary/lisbon_strategy_en.htm

14. European Union. (2014). *Latvia in the EU - 10 years later. A Different Latvia?* http://providus.lv/article_files/2721/original/Latvia_in_the_EU_10_years_brief.pdf?1415022500

15. FFH, F. (2018). Immigration and House Prices in the UK - Article Summary and Policy. *Journal of Political Sciences & Public Affairs*, 06(03). <https://doi.org/10.4172/2332-0761.1000334>

16. Golubeva, M. (2012). Consultative bodies and dialogue platforms for immigrant communities: lessons from three EU countries. *Centre for Public Policy PROVIDUS*, June. http://www.providus.lv/upload_file/Projekti/Eiropas_politika/2012/konsultativas_institucijas_angl.pdf

17. Ilona, K., Aija, L., Nils, M., & Sigita, Z.-O. (2009). Immigrant Integration

in Latvia. *Advanced Social and Political Research Institute (ASPRI, September.*

18. Investment and Tourism agency of Riga. (2020). *Tourism.*

19. Kährik, A., Kangur, K., & Leetmaa, K. (2019). Socio-economic and ethnic trajectories of housing estates in Tallinn, Estonia. In *Urban Book Series*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-23392-1_10

20. Kaša, R., & Mieriņa, I. (2019). The Emigrant Communities of Latvia. In *IMISCOE Research Series*. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007%2F978-3-030-12092-4>

21. Kesane, I., & Kasa, R. (2012). Learning to welcome: Integration of immigrants in Latvia. *Centre for Public Policy PROVIDUS*, 37–79.

22. Kort-Butler, L. A. (2017). Social Support Theory. *The Encyclopedia of Juvenile Delinquency and Justice*, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118524275.ejdj0066>

23. Lāce, A., Geks, R. F. (2018). Measuring and Improving integration of beneficiaries of international protection. Baseline assessment: Latvia, available at: <http://www.forintegration.eu/pl/pub>

24. Lee, E. (1966). A Theory of Migration. *Demography*, 3(1), 47-57. Retrieved from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2060063>

25. Lomas, T. (2016). The LIFE Model. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, January.

26. Lomas, T., Hefferon, K., & Ivtzan, I. (2015). The LIFE Model: A Meta-Theoretical Conceptual Map for Applied Positive Psychology. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 16(5), 1347–1364. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-014-9563-y>

27. Mangule, I., & Akule, D. (2014). Summary : Immigration in Latvia. *Centre for Public Policy PROVIDUS*, 1–9. http://www.integration.lv/uploads/files/informativie-materiali/2012/kopsavilkums_imigracija_latvija_en.pdf

28. Massey, D. S., Arango, J., Hugo, G., Kouaouci, A., Pellegrino, A., & Taylor, J. E. (2011). Theories of International Migration : and Appraisal.

Population English Edition, 19(3), 431–466. <http://www.jstor.org/pss/2938462>

29. McAuliffe, M., & Triandafyllidou, A. (2022). 2021. *World Migration Report 2022*. International Organization for Migration (IOM), Geneva.
30. Nicholas, H. Van, Oliver, B., & Katy, L. (2017). Push-pull plus : reconsidering the drivers of migration. *Centre on Migration, Policy and Society, (COMPAS), University of Oxford*, 1–34.
31. Parkins, N. C. (2010). Push and pull factors of migration. *American Review of Political Economy*, 8(2), 6.
32. Poon, J., & Garratt, D. (2012). Evaluating UK housing policies to tackle housing affordability. *International Journal of Housing Markets and Analysis*, 5(3), 253–271. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17538271211243599>
33. Sami, B. D. (2000). Migration Patterns and Challenges for Indians Seeking Work Abroad. *National Forum of Migrant Workers Rights*.
34. Tabuns, A., Ivanov, A., & Kiope, M. (2011). *Ethnic Identities and Integration*.
35. Thapan, M., & Deka, M. (2011). A View of Europe : Perspectives from Indian Immigrants. *EuroBroadMap*.
36. The UN Refugee Agency. (2021). Refugee Voices On Integration In Estonia, Latvia And Lithuania Results from the survey and profiling exercise. In *UNHCR Nordic and Baltic Countries*.
37. University of Latvia Press. (2010). How Integrated is Latvian Society? An Audit of Achievements, Failures and Challenges. In *University of Latvia Advanced Social and Political Research Institute*. – Riga: University of Latvia Press, 2010. – 292 pp. ISBN 978-9984-45-172-5. <https://doi.org/10.22364/hils>
38. Wilder, J. E. (2003). The Theoretical Basis for the Life Model. *The Complete Guide to Living With Men*, 1–8.
39. Xiana, B., & Prieto-rosas, V. (2019). Migration theories. *Encyclopedia of Gerontology and Population Aging*, 1–11.
40. Zepa, B. (2001). Integration policy in Latvia : theory and practice.

Integration The Vlsi Journal, 106–138.

41. Zepa, B., Šūpule, I., Kešāne, I., Lulle, A., Hazans, M., Ţabko, O., Bebrīša, I., & Krastiņa, L. (2009). *Immigrants in Latvia : Possibilities and Conditions*.